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Activation of SLC7A11 by HPV16 E7.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We demonstrate here through measurement of total transcription in cells expressing high-risk papillomavirus oncoproteins the activation of *Slc7a11* by HPV16 E7.

Citations

1. Zhou, N., Chen, J., Hu, M., Wen, N., Cai, W., Li, P., Zhao, L., Meng, Y., Zhao, D., Yang, X. and Liu, S., 2025. SLC7A11 is an unconventional H⁺ transporter in lysosomes. *Cell*, 188(13), pp.3441-3458.